

MEDIA PORTRAYAL OF THE #ENDSARS PROTEST IN NIGERIA: A CASE OF MAINSTREAM-TELEVISION COVERAGE VERSUS TWITTER

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ABSTRACT

In 2020 the Nigerian youths came together to protest against a unit of the Nigerian Police, Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS). They protested against police brutality and impunity suffered at the hands of this police unit. The protest lasted for weeks before it was brought to an abrupt and forceful halt after the Lekki Toll Gate massacre of 20 October 2020. This study looks at traditional news media coverage of the protest, and how global awareness was achieved through Twitter.

The study made use of quantitative content analysis to answer the research questions. A quantification of randomly selected hashtags was executed as well in an attempt to show the extent twitter was used during the peak period of the #EndSARS protest. Furthermore, the analysis and finding revealed a high percentage of poor and negative protester coverage by the news media, further delegitimising, villainising, and marginalising the protesters.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Although an apt and agreeable definition for the term ‘police brutality’ is yet to surface, Root (2015) describes police brutality as the use of unnecessary and excessive violence by the police. Abosede (2020) asserts that police brutality is a tool used to maintain a variety of systems of inequality and oppression in different societies. Agreeably, this tool - police brutality, is one that has become systematic. Police brutality in Nigeria has a history traced back to the military era, as well as political protests by the Nigerian citizens. Osha (2020) claims that colonial rule planted the seeds of “incessant violence, impunity, and factionalisation in the arbitrary territories that now make up modern Nigeria, before the military coups and countercoups that litter Nigeria’s disoriented political history”. Amidst the oppression, the colonial state then, did encounter resistance in the sense that demonstrators targeted court buildings, court officials, and isolated police personnel to register their resistance. One might see this as a reason for clampdown on protesters. He further claims that these protesters during the colonial era, engaged in acts of arson and vandalism aimed at symbols of colonial power, and as a revengeful response, colonial authorities systematically burnt and destroyed properties.

In the early days of the unit, the combat-ready SARS officers operated undercover in plain sight with no form of government insignia. Their main responsibility was to monitor radio communications and facilitate successful arrests of criminals. For 10 years, the Special AntiRobbery Squad - SARS only operated in Lagos state, but by 2002, the unit had spread to all 36 states of Nigeria, as well as the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. By then, its mandate as part of the Nigerian Police Force included arrests, investigation, and prosecution of suspected criminals. The perks of this responsibility endowed them with a level of power and authority. Hence, the unit moved from its major responsibilities, and perpetuated criminal activities which involved setting up roadblocks and extorting money from citizens. Officers remained in plain clothes but began appearing with arms in public (Aljazeera report, 2020). According to reports from Amnesty International, Nigerians had endured the menace constituted by this unit of the Nigerian Police Force, in hopes that the Nigerian Government would make do on promises of police reform since the early 2000s.

Chow (2020) affirms that in 2010, the Special Anti-Robbery Squad was called out by the Open Society Justice Initiative for operating with “pervasive corruption, destruction of evidence, and routine extortion”. He further explains that the then-president of Nigeria, Goodluck Jonathan pledged billions for the cause of police reform in the country (as seen on Time, 2020; TNV, 2010). However, after the statement was released, tension was reduced, as well as commotion. Soon after these claims by the president emeritus, new cases of police brutality by the Special Anti-Robbery Squad began surfacing again. Investigations executed by Amnesty International in 2010 implied that the Special Anti-Robbery Squad unit operated with impunity. This is because several Nigerian citizens, unregistered and in their custody, had gone missing. These allegations against the Special Anti-Robbery Squad continued to increase, so did Media reports from several national and international news media outlets. This implies that the reforms promised by the Federal Government of Nigeria were never executed.

Having established that the Government failed to take any decisive action toward holding the SARS unit accountable, Nigerian citizens took to their social media accounts and voiced out. This was in 2017, when the first #EndSARS tweet appeared. These tweets remained at a minimal level from 2017 up until 2020 when a video surfaced on social media platforms. The video showed a SARS operative shoot live rounds at an unarmed young man. This caused an uproar, and as a result, amplified the use of the hashtags “#EndSARS”, alongside others; “#SARSMustEnd”, “#EndPoliceBrutality”, “#EndSARSNOW”, “#EndBadGovernance” (Obia, 2020).

Shortly after, the demonstration made way to the streets on 8 October 2020. This occurred in various states of Nigeria including Lagos the commercial city of Nigeria, and Abuja the Federal Capital Territory. According to Jones (2021), the protesters who were mostly youths, demanded an end to police brutality in Nigeria and an end to the impunity enjoyed by the infamous police unit, SARS. The street demonstrations led by various public figures and activists continued despite the Nigerian Government’s attempt to bring it to a halt by use of tear gas and arrests. The demonstrations lasted for two weeks until the “20-10-20” incident.

20 October 2020 has become a day to remember for Nigerians and the world. The date is significant for the day the Nigerian Army opened fire / live rounds on unarmed peaceful protesters who gathered at the Lekki Toll Gate in Lagos Nigeria, singing the National anthem. This caused a controversy as there were little to no official news media coverage during the protests that led to this event. Hence the Nigerian Government easily denied the reports of the panel that investigated the scene and in fact confirmed the incidence. Although reports have shown the difficulties and casualties experienced by journalists in similar situations (e.g., Federation of Journalists – IFJ, 2020; Reporters Without Borders; Premium Times, 2020), the absence of proper and accurate reports from Nigeria’s national news media furthermore implies the ‘Protest Paradigm’ pattern during the #EndSARS protest of 2020.

1.2 Research Aims and Objectives

The study mainly aims to ascertain the pattern of traditional news media coverage of the #EndSARS protests in Nigeria, to seek if it fits into Chan and Lee’s (1984) concept of ‘protest paradigm’. This study also aims to ascertain how Twitter played a role in raising global awareness, thus combating media censorship and delegitimation during the 2020 #EndSARS protest in Nigeria. More so, I aim to achieve this through an analysis carried out on Nigerian traditional news media outlets, and a quantification of Twitter hashtags that aided in amplifying the protests. This research makes use of content analysis to answer the following research question as well as the sub-question:

1. How did social media and traditional media interact to depict the 2020 #EndSARS protest in Nigeria?
2. To what extent did traditional media coverage communicate the reason for the 2020 #EndSARS protest?
3. To what extent did Twitter play a role in raising global awareness during the 2020 #EndSARS protest in Nigeria?

1.3 The Rationale

Twitter has become a catalyst for social protests in developing and developed nations (Hari, 2014). This mirrors Habermas’s (1964) ‘public sphere’, which in this case implies that the social media platform has succeeded in creating a virtual space where individuals from different parts

of the world come together, share ideas, and engage in discourses that bring real change to society. Furthermore, Ijeoma (2021) concurs that Twitter has become the ‘Habermasian’ ideal which in this case, makes provision for citizens to critically communicate and analyse public and political matters. However, studies have shown that Twitter was the social media platform utilized the most to amplify the ‘#EndSARS’ protest and the demands of the Nigerian Youths who spearheaded the movement (e.g., Effiong, 2021; Asemah, Otinau, & Jumbo, 2022; Ayinde, 2021).

According to Browne (2011), the media has the vital role to play in promoting transparency and accountability. However, Khouri (1999), identifies four general media roles, of which includes the media’s role in political accountability by keeping an eye on public officials and challenging them through reports, as well as to inform the public. The question of transparency, accountability, and public’s trust of the media is brought up in national issues such as political protests, in this case, the #EndSARS protest. According to Balkin (2009), there are three types of media transparency: “Informational transparency, participatory transparency, and accountability transparency”. And when talking about public’s trust, the ‘watchdog’ concept of media reporters was brought to ridicule during the #EndSARS protest leading to the ‘20-10-20’ incidence. This, however, echoes the question of where the loyalty of the Nigerian media lies, and further suggests Chan and Lee’s (1984) ‘protest paradigm’ pattern.

Having stated these reasons, there is a need to further affirm that Twitter, unlike other social media platforms, has been integrated into Nigeria’s political discourse (Obia, 2020), and is described as a “land whose inhabitants are not subject to anyone’s control” (Opeibi, 2019). This will aid the study to affirm that Twitter was used to communicate the demands and reasons of the #EndSARS protest where the traditional media failed to. Furthermore, an analysis on the traditional media reports during the #EndSARS protest leading to the events of 20-10-20 will ultimately aid the study to ascertain if certainly, the media did not perform their duties as expected during the #EndSARS protest of 2020. This will ultimately prove or disprove the protest paradigm pattern during the protests.

1.4 Structure of Research

This research paper consists of 6 chapters: The introductory chapter which provides a detailed background to the study, its aims and objectives, and the rationale behind the study; The second chapter is the literature review, which provides a detailed and explanatory collection of literature and empirical studies, and portrays a critical overview of key concepts, further identifying gaps in the research; The third chapter is the methodology, which gives detail to the research methods used for the study, the sample selection, the coding process, discussion of ethics and ethical procedures, and consideration of methodological limitations; The fourth chapter is the analysis carried out on traditional news media reports; The fifth chapter is the analysis carried out on Twitter to establish extent of hashtag usage. This will be achieved through quantification of tweets and retweets of selected hashtags on twitter; The sixth and final chapter is the conclusion and recommendation of the study, which points out limitations of the study, and further recommends research that could be birthed from the questions raised in the literature review, and findings from the analysis.

CHAPTER 2

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 POLITICAL PROTESTS IN NIGERIA

Political Protest, although with a broad meaning, can be identified as a form of political participation other than the nuanced forms of political participation such as democracy, elections, and voting. Kaase and Marsh (1979), define Political protest as all voluntary activities by individual citizens intended to influence either directly or indirectly political choices at various levels of political system. Gabriel, Keil, and Kerrouche (2012), further suggest that issues that involve political participation can lead to either conventional political protest or to more dramatic forms of political violence. In this case, the incessant trail of political protest in Nigerian history. Nigeria, like other countries, has a history of political protests informed by various reasons and causes up until recent times.

The first recorded protest in Nigerian history is one not to forget in a hurry. Termed “**The Aba Women’s Rebellion of 1929**”, where the market women of south-eastern Nigeria stood up against the British colonial government for imposition of tax policies on women, who were taxexempt in the Igbo culture of Nigeria. This was because they did not make as much as the male counterparts, and physically intense jobs were delegated on biological premise. Historians and researchers have given accounts to this rebellion and have indeed marked it as the first political protest in Nigeria. Obienusi (p. 131) asserts that the Women’s Rebellion of 1929 marked an apex in women’s resistance in eastern Nigeria to colonial rule. However, historians have also given account of bloodshed during the protest. Evans (2009) details that, during the protest in November of 1929, while the Aba women in their thousands had gathered, the colonial police and troops were called in, and opened fire on the crowd. It is recorded that more than 50 lost their lives, and over 50 were badly injured.

Several other notable political protests are scattered over Nigeria’s history, including the ‘Ali Must Go protest of 1978’, ‘June 12 1993 protest’, ‘Occupy Nigeria protest’, and most recently, the “#EndSARS protest”. However, these protests share a similarity. A pattern. For example, for each of these protests, the Nigerian citizens attempt to stand up against oppression and corruption that prevails within the Nigerian Government but are suppressed by the Nigerian

Army or the Nigerian Police Force which are part of the Nigerian Government. Prominently, we find that in all these protests, there are recorded deaths as a result of clampdown by the military forces or the Nigerian Police force. Thus, in concurrence, Iwuoha and Anichie (2021) refers to Nigeria as a repressive state. That is, the citizens of Nigeria only have limited freedom, which is a contradictory breach of the State's human right's constitution, and in general, a violation of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) Nigeria

Like many countries, the foremost law enforcement agency in Nigeria is the police force. In this case, the Nigerian Police Force (NPF). This is in accordance with Part III of Section 214 of the Nigerian Constitution of 1999 (NigeriaLaw.org). The major responsibility of the Nigerian Police Force entails maintaining law and order, as well as protecting the citizens of Nigeria. However, existing under the umbrella of the Nigerian Police Force, are subsidiary units endowed with their own various responsibilities. To mention a few; department of Federal Operations, Boarder Patrol Section, Police Mobile Force, Counter-Terrorism Unit, Special Protection Unit, and dissolved recently in 2020, the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS). The Nigerian Police Force (2019) stipulates that their main goal is to create a safe and secure environment for everyone living in Nigeria. The statement is contradicted, as Amusan and Saka (2020) argue that the Nigerian police is extremely corrupt and the corruption that persist within ranks, high or low, within the Nigerian police force, knows no bounds. They further argue in their study on 'The Nigerian Police Force and the Task of Policing Democratic Nigeria', that the use of force by the police against Nigerians has become a norm, and there is no sustained effort at addressing the problem. An example can be drawn from the now dissolved, infamous Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) unit of the Nigerian Police Force.

SARS is an acronym for Special Anti-Robbery Squad. It was a Unit of the Nigerian Police Force, created in 1992 by now retired, former Commissioner of Police - Simeon Danladi. This was during a period where crime was on the rise in Nigeria, and armed robbers and bandits terrorized Lagos State and some other southern Nigerian states. Obiakor (2021) accounts that the combat-ready SARS officers operated undercover in plain clothing and plain, un-crested vehicles without government insignia. This was a method of undercover activities by this unit

of the Nigerian Police Force, where they had the leverage of easily blending into communities, unsuspected. She further states that the SARS unit operated successfully for ten years, of during which this period the unit had spread to all 36 states of Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory Abuja.

The first series of crimes committed by SARS, recorded in the early 2000s, is said to have been attributed to the brutal methods of policing during the military era, which some researchers have attributed to the British Colonial Era, before Nigeria got independence in 1960 (Osha 2020). As aforementioned, by 2002, SARS had spread all through Nigeria, and had become an authoritative figure of law enforcement as well. Malumfashi (2020) details that the unit by then was counted as one of the 14 major units under the Nigerian Police Force Criminal Investigation and intelligence Department. Their mandate included arrests, investigation and persecution of suspected armed robbers, murderers, kidnappers, hired assassins and other suspected violent criminals. He further explains that emboldened by its powers, the unit moved on from what was originally their mandate and intentionally began constituting nuisance. Operatives of this unit began carrying arms boldly in public, setting up roadblocks and extorting citizens, all while not on any uniforms or without presentation of authoritative badge. The impunity enjoyed by the Special Anti-robbery Squad persisted for years and only became worse in the later 2010's, even amidst consistent claims of the Nigerian Government with intentions for police reform since far back as 2006 (Obiakor, Chikwendu, & Obienusi, 2021).

As of 2017, the Special Anti-Robbery Squad directed their attention toward the Nigerian Youths and began targeting mostly young men. "This was simply on the evidence of their owning a laptop or smartphone, or driving porch cars" (Malumfashi, 2020). Accounts given by reporters and scholars agree with that of Malumfashi's. Egbas (2019) further details how members of this Nigerian police unit would profile and beat up young Nigerians on account of their dreadlocks and tattoos. By that time, Any Nigerian youth in possession of any of the aforementioned items, or anyone fitting to the description were at risk. It is however of pertinence to recall that, in 2016, the United States charged 80 people, 77 of which were Nigerians for internet scams of about 46 million dollars (Aljazeera, 2019). This was also the period that Nigeria was infamously known for cyber-fraud popularly dubbed "Nigerian Prince", or "Yahoo!". Perhaps this gave the Special Anti-Robbery Squad - SARS a reason to violently prey on the Nigerian youths.

Some scholars argue that SARS was a responsible unit that carried out their duties with diligence. They are credited with fighting of violent crimes such as armed robbery and kidnappings, which resulted in drastic reduction of incidents of the crimes on a nationwide level (Obiakor, Chikwendu, & Obienusi, 2021). However, to other scholars like Anichie & Iwuoha (2021), the crimes and impunity perpetrated by SARS were nothing other than police brutality in a repressive state. Through witness / survivor interactions and investigations, International human rights advocate organizations such as Human Rights Watch (2000), and Amnesty International (2020) have documented a barrage of cases of police brutality at an inhumane level committed by SARS. Cases such as arbitrary and extrajudicial killings, public and private harassment, excessive use of force, abduction, illegal arrest and detention, rape, torture, and other forms of human rights violations.

#ENDSARS Protest of 2020

According to Vega (2020), the first #ENDSARS hashtag appeared in 2017 when Nigerian activists created the Twitter campaign. Oloyede and Elega (2019) maintain that the campaign began with convener, Segun Awosanya. This happened shortly after a tech personnel was wrongly profiled and harassed. In her report, Vega further explains that the reason behind this campaign was to pressure the Nigerian Government and the Nigerian Police Force to disband the Special Anti-Robbery Squad unit. However, the campaign remained at a minimal level until 2020. On the 4th of October 2020, a footage of SARS officials shooting a young man in Delta State Nigeria, surfaced on Twitter. This caused an upheaval, which as a result, boosted the #EndSARS hashtag.

According to news reports from international media outlets such as BBC (2021), Aljazeera (2020), and The Times (2020), Demonstrations across major cities began on 8 October 2020. Protesters began demonstrating in cities across Nigeria. The number of Nigerian youths that poured out into major Nigerian roads, causing major roadblocks, and fuelling the protest informed the notion of a lasting political unrest. Obia (2020) recalls that the Police Chief, Mohammed Adamu made announcements concerning the dissolution of SARS on 11 October 2020. However, the protesters did not back down. This could be relative to the past promises of

the Nigerian Government to disband the SARS unit and reform the police since far back as 2006. The protesters only continued to increase in number. The number of demonstrators alongside the maximization of social media garnered global awareness. Kabir (2020) maintains that the #EndSARS protest gained global recognition due to unified agenda, economic effect, persistence, high unemployment and poverty rate, coordination and logistics, support from Nigerians in diaspora, and the use and utilization of social media extensively. He further explains that, amidst misinformation and disinformation, the use of social media in the #EndSARS protest was revolutionary to the movement.

While some scholars claim that the #EndSARS hashtag garnered more tweets than the #BlackLivesMatter outcry (Kabir,2020), some scholars suggest a similarity of the #EndSARS protest to that of #BlackLivesMatter's George Floyd, although with a contrast of racial prejudice in the United States. Abosede (2020) suggests the similarities as "triggered by the impunity of police violence upon marginalised communities, both movements featured dramatic outpouring of young people, both movements made savvy use of social media". In this case, the marginalised Nigerian youths maximised and utilized the use of social media platforms. Eligon (2020) maintains that this is because a widespread, worldwide protest began with a hashtag - #BlackLivesMatter. This ultimately implies the use of 'Hashtag Activism'.

2.2 HASHTAG ACTIVISM AND POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

The literature for Hashtag Activism and Political Participation is essential to the development of this research, as it is of key importance to the #EndSARS protest of 2020. This will enable readers to comprehend the use of alternative media for political or moral causes, as well as educate readers and researchers on the pros and cons of the hashtag activism. This will be achieved through a brief history of Hashtags, what they were created for, the impact they can create when used and amplified, and in what ways they can be used. For this research, the literature here will make use of comparisons between western countries and Nigeria.

Having knowledge about the functions of the hashtag '#', as well as knowledge about activism, one can easily put together "the use of social media hashtags to mobilise, sensitise, and build public support or response for a political cause", as hashtag activism. Since the advent of

technology, and much later, digital media, the world has gradually been reduced to a global village. And in modern day society, communication technologies have become a major part of important innovations (Dambo et al., 2021), as well as change. Although originally created for connecting with friends and family, social media / social networking sites today are used for a variety of things ranging from news, entertainment, business, and politics. Social Networking Sites (SNS) have become a space for people to exchange ideas, discuss topics of interest, and build connections on the premise of these discussions. This means social media can bring people together for a cause.

According to the Freedom Forum Institute, the first amendment defends individuals from government censorship, as everyone is entitled to freedom of expression, as well as freedom of speech. A similar is seen in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Chapter 4, Section 39 under the 'Fundamental Rights' clause which states "every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression, including freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart ideas and information without interference". The Nigerian constitution further states that "every person shall be entitled to own, establish and operate any medium for the dissemination of information, ideas, and opinions". Although with clear rules set to regulate the execution of this constitution, it is agreeable that everyone is entitled to their opinion, as much as they are entitled to expressions and freedom of speech on social media platforms. There is a catch. Social media platforms are private owned. That is, they might not be owned completely by a single individual, but they are not owned by any government body as well (Freedom Forum Institute). This means that social media platforms and their operations are not subject to change by any government body. Although there is a statutory code of practice for providers of social media platforms (GOV.UK, 2019). The governing of these platforms rather, are guided by policies set in place by regulatory departments of these platforms, in compliance with the code of practice. Nonetheless, I find that for every social media platform, via user policies, every user is entitled to free speech and is only subject to censorship, moderation, or account expulsion when making use of hate-speech, life threats, deliberate misinformation, and harassment.

Indeed, social media today, has become a place where users freely express themselves. social media users express themselves through the sharing of ideas and interests which is typically conveyed in forms of texts or visuals. Using Habermas' (1964, p.49) Public Sphere, it is safe to say that social media has become a place where "private individuals assemble to form a public

body”. Habermas further maintains that individuals in a public sphere do not identify professionally, neither are they subject to the legal constraints of a state’s bureaucracy. In agreement to that, scholars suggest that social media sites are organized in ways that meet the requisites of a public sphere (Kruse, Norris, and Flinchum, 2018). As what should be described as a revolution today, for over a decade, these social media platforms have made it possible for activists to create and promote campaigns all over the world. Campaigns that have brought success to the causes. An example is the MeToo movement of 2006. Social media platforms have also given a voice to marginalized and minority groups as well. An example is the #BlackLivesMatter campaign of 2012, and most recently in Nigeria, the #EndSARS protest of 2020.

Hashtags have existed prior its use on social networking site platforms. But they were mainly used by programmers, and on coding back-ends. Today, the hashtag is a Twitter feature that allows users to streamline their tweets around a single theme, issue, or focus (Goswami, 2018). However, the hashtags on social media were first introduced by Chris Messina, a programmer who originally suggested the idea to Twitter, as a way of easily categorizing and finding specific content on the social media platform, Twitter. According to Lips (2018), the hashtag comes from “programmer culture”. She further expatiates that Twitter did not always have the hashtag feature we know and use today, and that the introduction of the hashtag was an attempt to solve a problem of complaints by users who were not particularly excited about the sort of irrelevant and random contents they were exposed to. In an interview with Chris Messina conducted by CNBC (2018), it is revealed that the initial idea for the hashtag was turned down by Twitter, but Chris saw an opportunity and utilized it on the same social media platform. Since then, the social media hashtag usage has become a trend. Today, social media users utilize this feature for several reasons involving politics, fashion, self-promotion etc. An example is during the 2016 US presidential election. Hashtags such as #iamwithher, #MakeAmericaGreatAgain, #Feelthebern were all used to amplify voices and support during presidential election campaign period. This suggests the use of the hashtag feature for activism or political participation.

Hashtag Activism in Nigeria

Goswami (2018) elaborates extensively on the concepts of Hashtag Activism in her publication “Social Media and Hashtag Activism”. She further establishes that the hashtag is no longer just a symbol or a sign, it has evolved into a tool used to draw attention and participation for a cause

over social media platform. In this case, Twitter. Goswami further contrasts the traditional forms of activism, to the hashtag activism which does not necessarily require any action other than “Sharing, Liking, or Retweeting”, or even the use of the hashtag as well. Although, it is arguable that the use of the hashtag for activism on social media have influenced several notable protests and demonstrations. Tremayne (2014) identifies the #OccupyWallStreet (OWS) protest as the first hashtag protest. Here, he details the timeline of events that led to the #OccupyWallStreet demonstrations that occurred in September of 2011. This was after a blog post by Adbusters, and an accompanying Twitter message that included the hashtag. He further describes how after these tweets had gained momentum; a fraction of the online voices made their way to Wall Street on 17 September. He further describes this as “a turnout of sufficient size to disrupt business, gain attention, provoke a police response and ultimately to swell their ranks”. The aforementioned research vividly aids in proving how with a hashtag, an online rally and mobilization can be achieved, and ultimately how such social media activities can be cause for physical action and demonstration. The ‘Occupy’ protest was one of notability, as the #OccupyWallStreet protest which had gained global attention, was the advent of several ‘#Occupy’ protests in several countries around the world (Tremayne, 2014). A vivid example of this is the #OccupyNigeria protest of 2012. Furthermore, this implies the use of hashtag activism in Nigeria.

The #OccupyNigeria protest was the first of its kind in Nigeria. A protest amplified using social media hashtag. Dubbed as the “Nigeria’s Harmattan” (Ifejika, 2012), Motilola (2013) concurs that the Occupy Nigeria protest did not last as long as the Arab Spring but still gained global attention. The occupy Nigeria protest was against the prevailing economic hardship at the time. This was the period of which the global ‘Occupy’ protest earlier mentioned was still ongoing. Some scholars argue the authenticity of the use of social media for democratization. On that note, Russell (2011) believes that networked journalism is the general publics, playing the roles of creators, reactors, (re)makers and (re)distributors of news and where all variety of media, amateurs and professional, corporate, and independent products, and interests intersect at a new level (Motilola, 2013). These scholars’ arguments are on the purview that the general public might take over the roles of the press. Sunstein (2001) argues firmly that when audience tend to report their versions of reality, it results in the same audience consuming only those stories they want to see or hear. This implies the prevalence of fake news. He further claims that the internet and other forms of alternative news outlets wreak havoc on democracies. Motilola

(2013) further points at Fenton's (2008, 238) compliance to Sunstein (2001), where he states that amidst the internet offering provision for mobilization, its potential to encourage democracy "is not dependent on its primary features of interactivity, multiplicity and polycentricity, which are often celebrated and heralded as offering intrinsic democratic benefit".

Granted, political participation with the use of social media has its pitfalls. Regardless, this method of modern-day political participation - hashtag activism has been a catalyst for change in several cases, in several countries. For instance, the #OccupyWallStreet protest presented a decentralized form of movement organizing that enabled hundreds of city chapters to reinforce and strengthen one another yet remain independent. This, a sharp break from the traditional structure of protest movements of the past (Levitin, 2021). Although the fights for racial equality have long persisted, Racism/Racial prejudice are still very much existent in modern society. Notably so, there have been some improvements over the years. Jaia (2020) concurs that the #BlackLiveMatters movement, otherwise dubbed as BLM reckoned an increased support as well as global participation, defunding of the police, removing of confederate statuses and symbols, racial reckoning across industries, and international solidarity. Ankel (2020) supports by stating the changes made by several police departments in the US. An example among others, is defunding of the police and police reforms, an eradication and ban of the chokehold practice, and the Justice in policing Act of 2020, which eliminates unannounced police raids and makes it easier for them - the police to be prosecuted if in breach of this act. These were achievements garnered because of the #BlackLivesMatters protest in 2020. A protest which gained so much global attention within the span of one month. Pew Research Centre (2020) provides an analysis to support this. An analysis carried out on publicly available tweets within that timeline, that shows the use of the '#BlackLivesMatter' hashtag. From May 26, 2020, to June 7, 2020, the hashtag was used 47.8 million times on Twitter alone. That is an average of 3.7 million times a day (Pew Research Centre, 2020). This paints a vivid picture of the kind of social media amplification achieved during the period.

Indeed, social media has become a tool for individuals to easily have a voice and express themselves, as well as engage in political discourse. This references Harbemas's 'Public Sphere' once more. Several countries across the world have engaged in this new form of political participation - hashtag activism. This includes the #OccupyNigeria,

#BringBackOurGirls, and most recently, the #EndSARS protests of Nigeria. These protests did not just gain global recognition, but catalysed change during their time. The #EndSARS protest being the most recent, Obia (2020) maintains that twitter was used majorly in three ways; to co-ordinate protests, to amplify the voice of the campaign globally, and to berate brands and public figures deemed to be opposed to the movement. Referring to the Nigerian Twitter users as the “Nigerian Twittersphere”, Obia’s analysis found that Nigerian social media users use Twitter differently than other social media platforms. Perhaps it is suggestive to note that this is as a result of the difference between Twitter’s moderation regulations and that of its counterparts. He further acknowledges that Nigerians use Twitter in a particularly ‘activist, aggressive, and confrontational’ way. Furthermore, the #EndSARS protest resulted in the permanent dissolution of the Special Anti-Robbery Squad - SARS (Jones, 2020), the police unit responsible for the reason behind the #EndSARS protest, and cased with litter of unaccounted crimes over the years.

2.3 SOCIAL MEDIA COVERAGE AND POLITICAL PROTESTS

Today, a piece of news can simply be a hyperlink or a 280 character-long tweet (Mahid, Manickam, and Karuppayah, 2018). Although social media users are entitled to freedom of expression as well as freedom of speech on social media platforms, and as much as social media has become a public sphere as earlier ascertained, some scholars and researchers are concerned about the use of social media for political participation. For instance, Anderson (2005) and Hermida (2009) have heavily criticized ‘citizen journalism’, and this is entirely on the premise of what is real and what is not. That is, fake news. For instance, the authenticity of the 2016 US presidential election has long been questioned. An analysis presented by Read (2016), states the use of social media ‘parody sites’ to disclose and “circulate throughout Facebook: The Pope Endorses Trump, Hillary Clinton bought \$137m in illegal arms, The Clintons bough a \$200m house in the Maldives”. He further asserts the number of reactions, as in likes and comments these posts made, as ridiculous as the false news stories and headlines were. Mahid, Manickam, and Karuppayah (2018) concur, maintaining that the concern on the amplification of fake news is rational, considering the vast growth and proliferation of the internet and wide use of social media. Does this mean that the spread of fake news is pivotal to manipulating audience perception?

The Black Lives Matter protest of 2020, a movement that shook the world (Gottbrath, 2020), now dubbed as “one of the largest political movements in history” (Woolerton, 2022), is one that cannot be forgotten. Originally founded in 2013, the major aim of this Global Network Foundation is to eradicate white supremacy and build local power in response to violence inflicted on Black communities and minorities (Black Lives Matter). Although several Black Lives Matter related protests occurred before the most notable of 2020, researchers found that police-caused deaths predict protest activities (Williamson, Trump, and Einstein, 2018). Some researchers claim the Black Lives Matter protest of 2020 was because of reactions to the murder of George Floyd on May 25, 2020 (Woolerton, 2020), while some claim it was as a result of pent-up tension from the murder of Breonna Taylor earlier the same year, and later on, that of George Floyd (Gottbrath, 2020). Arguably, both claims are affirmative, as both murders were executed by police officers, and studies show the psychological impact such forms of racial prejudice can cause for Black people (Pazzanese, 2021). This resulted in the mass protests and demonstrations that followed the video of George Floyd’s murder was shared across social media platforms. Research from the Pew Research Centre (2020) found that within two days, the hashtag ‘#BlackLivesMatter’ was used on Twitter 8.8 million times. Insights to the global recognition this protest achieved was established earlier on. Nonetheless, it is safe to suggest that with this type of popularity comes its pitfalls.

Georgacopoulos and Poche (2020) asserts that civil unrest provides opportune moment for bad actors to spread disinformation and to divide society. This means that when there are political movements such as the Black Lives Matter, people with malicious intentions and ulterior motives are bound to react as well. Georgacopoulos and Poche further buttress this by enumerating and explaining the list of fake news during the #BlackLivesMatter protest: “Tear gas, George Floyd Not Dead, Soros Conspiracy, ANTIFA conspiracy, Wild Fakes”. Agreeably, social media spreads information faster than traditional media. A study carried out by ProCon.org shows that 78% of traditional media reporters use social media to check for breaking news. The proliferation of manufactured or misleading videos and content on social media has become a common feature of social protests (Bello and Reuters, 2021). To comprehend this, we take the case of the 2021 Cuba protest for instance. There were reports of fake news by international media outlets. A report from Aljazeera states that the Cuban government claimed the fake news was spread by counterrevolutionaries, meanwhile Bello and

Reuters (2021) concur with the government critics who suggest that “authorities could be planting the stories to muddy online waters with misinformation and sow confusion so that no one trusts future news of unrest” from social media platforms. Can the same be said for Nigeria during the 2020 #EndSARS protest?

According to Adegboruwa (2021), the Lagos State Judicial Panel of Inquiry and Restitution for Victims of SARS Related Abuses was officially inaugurated on 19 October 2020. This panel was endowed with the responsibility of investigation on the Lekki Toll Gate massacre which occurred on 10 October 2020. That is, the panel’s major responsibility was to either affirm or deny claims of ‘the shooting of unarmed protesters. However, the complete report from the panel affirms these claims (Lagos State Judicial Panel of Inquiry, 2020). Regardless of the result presented by the panel, the Federal Government flagged it as fake news. A media coverage by TVC News Nigeria (2021) during a press conference shows the Minister of Information and Culture of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Lai Mohammed, clearly stating that the incident of 20 October 2020 is “simply unverified fake news circulating and playing on social media”.

With this, he referred to the graphic videos of Nigerian citizens in possession of the Nation’s flag, drenched in blood. This, however, was the peak period of the #EndSARS protest which by then, had several international celebrities, philanthropists, activists, and politicians taking to their social media platforms to show support (Skinner, 2020). The authenticity and originality of the social media content which was in circulation during the aforementioned period further confirms the claims of the Lekki Toll Gate Massacre. This is because international media outlets such as CNN, Aljazeera, Amnesty International, and BBC had local correspondents and eyewitness reports. Furthermore, we find that these reports correspond regarding timeline and events. Perhaps it is of necessity to raise the question of how the Nigerian traditional media covered the protest.

2.4 MAINSTREAM MEDIA COVERAGE AND POLITICAL PROTESTS

Chan and Lee (1984) describe the concept of ‘Protest Paradigm’ as the pattern of delegitimizing news coverage or protests and dissent, which may majorly influence the society’s acceptance or rejection of protesters (McLeod and Hertog, 1992). The protest paradigm has become a pattern identified and dissected by a barrage of scholars and researchers over the years (e.g.,

Tubbs, 2020; Boykoff, 2006; Small, 1995). These scholars have criticized the mainstream media for further marginalizing and delegitimizing protests through portraying these protests as deviant, threatening, or impotent (Lee, 2014). Harlow et al (2020) asserts that how journalists cover protests and social movements matter a lot, because the more delegitimizing the coverage is, the less likely the public is to support the cause. These researchers found that the type of protest, location, and type of media outlet were significantly related to whether the stories behind the protest stuck to the protest paradigm (Harlow et al, 2020). They further discovered a pattern of negative protest coverage, especially in cases where these protests are ‘anti-status quo’. In such situations, the actual cause of the protest and what protesters are demanding, tend to get marginalized and disregarded due to the protesters’ negative portrayal by the news media.

The role of traditional media has been questioned repeatedly on the premise of protest coverage in countries where these protests occur. The emergence of notable protests such as the Arab Spring and Occupy Movement, as well as other national and international protests raise questions of media freedom within those countries (Muratoglu, 2021), and furthermore if the government has a hold on the media. Muratoglu further explains that these questions also arise from the true and accurate representation of the protests by the international news organizations, just as earlier mentioned in the case of the #EndSARS protest. Relating this to modern day events, an example is the 2020 #EndSARS protest of Nigeria. Several reports from media outlets confirm the reception of a letter from the National Broadcasting Commission of Nigeria, NBC, the parent regulatory body responsible for media organizations in Nigeria. This letter presented guides in regard to the protest coverage, stipulating “broadcasters should not embarrass individuals, organizations, government, or cause disaffection, incite to panic or rift in the society at large”, and further stating that “Broadcasters have a duty to promote the corporate existence of Nigeria, and the socio-economic well-being of the Nigerian State” (e.g, TheCable, 2020; PremiumTimesNG, 2021; The Sun, 2020). This had however, set the usual protest paradigm narrative, and in this case, the absence of the mainstream media informed the idea that the mainstream media had declared themselves on the side of the government (Olasoji, 2020), and with the absence of the media that should have covered the protest to relay the demands of the protesters, these protesters turned to an alternative source, social media.

Interestingly, media outlets in Nigeria like Arise TV, Channels TV, and African Independent Television - AIT, that reported on the events of the Lekki Toll Gate massacre that occurred during the protest were sanctioned by the NBC (PremiumTimes reports, 2020), and further fined a sum of 3 million Naira each. Other media organizations; The Guardian, (2020); This Day, (2020); Vanguard, (2020) affirm this report. The coverages reported and published by the aforementioned media organizations were from witnesses. That is, the same coverage published by their international counterparts, CNN, Aljazeera, and BBC. This however, echoes Mare's (2013) findings of how social media during a protest can act as public sphere for both citizens and professional journalists. These facts about the #EndSARS protest and media coverage fits into Smith et al's (2001) findings, which further echo a cue of research on how mainstream media tend to undermine protest movements (Boykoff, 2006; Gitlin, 1980), it also buttresses Lee's (2014) description of 'selection bias' as "the factors influencing whether a protest would feature in the news or not.

Furthermore, Chan and Lee (1984) argue that the mainstream media are agents of 'social control' which means that the mainstream media are responsible for maintaining existing norms and values, and support established institutions and systems. Bagdikian (2004) and Baker (1996) further concur that the media takes up the role of social control because of the embedding of media organisations in vast political economic set-ups.

CHAPTER 3

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Method of Analysis: Quantitative Content Analysis

The study will ultimately make use of a quantitative content analysis approach to; explore the pattern of traditional news media coverage in Nigeria during the 2020 #EndSARS protest, and the use of Twitter to communicate the demands of protesters as well as amplify the protest. This will ideally prove or disprove the pattern of Chan & Lee's (1984) 'protest paradigm'. Berelson (1952) defines Content Analysis as a research technique for the objective, systematic, and quantitative description of the manifest content of communication. Krippendorff (2004) further asserts that content analysis implies the 'systematic reading' of a body of texts, images, and symbolic matter, not necessary from an author's or user's perspective. Furthermore, Content Analysis is useful in social research topics when it comes to exploring trends and patterns (Bryman, Sloan, & Clark, 2021).

Quantitative content analysis, therefore, is a research method in which features of textual, visual, or aural materials are systematically categorised and recorded so they can be analyzed (Kevin & Scacco, 2017). Riffe et al (2014) further asserts that quantitative content analysis is the systematic and replicable examination of symbols of communication, which have been given numeric values according to valid measurement rules and the analysis of relationships involving those values, by use of statistical methods. Quantitative content analysis is often deductive (Bryman, 2021). By way of being deductive, it implies that quantitative content analysis uses an approach to the relationship between theory and research in which the researcher conducts the study with reference to hypotheses or ideas that have been inferred from theory.

Quantifying of texts through content analysis will allow for a systematic and intuitive view of the characteristics and dimension of texts, which will in turn permit the exploration of social impact as well as the connections between texts and reality (Hansen and Machin, 2019). However, Hansen and Machin (2019) further imply that the explicit nature of content analysis depicts "the indication of relative prominences and absences of key characteristics in media texts". Having established this, the combining, categorising, statistical presentations, and

analysing of published media texts from traditional news media sources, and existing data from Twitter, by means of quantitative content analysis will ultimately play a pivotal role in answering the research questions.

3.2 Method of Data Collection, Sampling and Choice of Samples: Simple Random Sampling

The research design essentially includes objectives, sampling, research strategies, tools, and techniques for collecting the evidence, analysing the data, and reporting the findings (Singh, 2006, 77). According to Bryman, Sloan, and Foster (2021), Sampling in research is described as a “smaller and ideally representative part of a bigger whole population”. This is relative to Cochran’s (1953) description of sampling in social sciences as being limited to workable numbers. He states that “it is not possible to collect data from every respondent relevant to the study but only from some fractional part of the respondents”. This further implies that sampling is a subset of the main population. However, identifying a representative sample that accurately reflects the population to be studied, effectively taking the form of the population in miniature, is a key role in sampling (Bryman, Sloan, and Foster, 2021).

To achieve a valid conclusion from conducting a content analysis, it is necessary to select the type of sample most suitable for the research questions. Majorly, there are two types of sampling methods: **Probability Sampling** and **Non-Probability Sampling**. There are four types of Probability Sampling Methods: **Simple Random Sample, Systematic Sample, Stratified Random Sampling, and Multi-stage Cluster Sampling**, and four under Non-Probability Sampling Methods: **Convenience Sampling, Voluntary Response Sampling, Purposive Sampling, Snowball Sampling** (Bryman, Sloan & Clark, 2021). They assert that under the probability sampling method; the simple random sample is the most basic form of probability sampling where each unit is selected by chance and each unit has a known and equal probability of being selected.

For this research, I made use of Simple Random Sampling, which falls under Probability Sampling. With the news media outlets in Nigeria as the population (e.g., Bryman, 2021), I made use of Krippendorff’s (2004, pp.114) ‘*Throwing Dice*’ method to select the sample unit of

7 by way of applying randomisation. The make-up of this number is sample units selected from privately owned, government-owned, and internationally operated news media outlets:

1. Private owned: The Guardian NG, Arise News Nigeria
2. Government-owned: Nigerian Tribune, This Day, The Nation
3. International operated: BBC News, CNN

A sample size of 181 was selected for this research. Using consecutive day sampling, which is a method of selecting a convenience sample of 7 or more consecutive days (Kim, Jang, & Kim, 2018), a period of 30 days' worth of media reports, textual commentaries, and news articles from the aforementioned media outlets has been selected. To further explain, this means I have consecutively selected the period starting from 8 October 2020 to 6 November 2020. This is the equivalent of a month's worth of news reports and coverage on the 2020 #EndSARS protest.

The quantitative analysis on Twitter consists of randomly selected hashtags. These hashtags convey meanings that serve as reasons behind the protest, as well as a cause, as in hashtag activism. For example, “#EndSARS” means “**End the Special Anti-Robbery Squad unit**”. Another example is “#EndPoliceBrutalityinNigeria”, which means “**End Police brutality in Nigeria**”, and “#endsarsprotest” means “**The protest calling for the end of the Special AntiRobbery Squad**”. However, to strictly conduct a quantitative analysis (and nothing more) on these hashtags, the tweets and retweets will be quantified. That is, the use of these hashtags during a specified period dating from 8 October 2020 to 6 November 2020. This is simply to reflect the extent of the use of Twitter during the #EndSARS protest, further allowing us to comprehend other researchers' claims as to how the protesters and activists succeeded in communicating the reasons behind the protest, as well as mobilising and raising awareness. The hashtags used for the quantification are #EndSARS, #endsars, #endpolicebrutality, #endpolicebrutalityinnigeria, #endsarsimmediately, #endsarsnow, #endsarsprotests, #endswat, #sarsmustend, and #sarsmustendnow.

3.3 Data Collection, Coding Categories, and Analysis Procedure Table 1: Framework of codes

FRAMING	ITEMS CODED FOR, PER FRAME	CASE
	DEPICTION OF PROTESTERS	No / Invalid Mention = 0 Protest and Demonstrations = 1 Violence on protesters = 2 Violence by protesters = 3 Attack on police = 4 Use of ammunitions on protesters = 5 ‘Peaceful protesters’ = 6 ‘Unarmed protesters’ = 7 Demographic of protesters = 8 Destruction of properties by protesters = 9 Destruction of properties by thugs = 10 Protesters arrested = 11 Lekki toll gate massacre = 12
	No Mention = 0 Responsible for criminal activities during protest = 1 Not responsible for criminal activities during protest = 2 Mix up of criminals during protest = 3 Mention of activists = 4 Mention of protesters = 5 International reach = 6 Other = 7	
	REASON FOR PROTEST	
PROTESTERS	No / Invalid Mention = 0 #EndSARS = 1 Calling for the end to SARS,	Police brutality = 13 Other = 14

	<p>Special AntiRobbery Squad = 2</p> <p>Extortion by SARS = 3</p> <p>Extra Judicial Killing = 4</p> <p>Impunity = 5</p> <p>Calling for the end to corruption = 6</p> <p>Calling for accountability of the government = 7</p> <p>Calling for an end to police brutality = 8</p> <p>Calling for the disbandment of SARS = 9</p> <p>Human rights =</p> <p>10 other = 11</p>	
	<p>SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE</p>	
	<p>1=YES</p> <p>0=NO</p>	
	<p>DEPICTION OF GOVERNMENT</p>	

<p>GOVERNMENT</p>	<p>No Mention = 0</p> <p>Responsible for criminal activities during protest = 1</p> <p>Responsible for fatalities and deaths during protests = 2</p> <p>Not responsible for criminal</p>	
	<p>activities during protest = 3</p> <p>Not responsible for fatalities and deaths during protest = 4</p> <p>Accountability = 5</p> <p>Mention of government officials = 6</p> <p>Government official against the protest = 7</p> <p>Government official in support of the protest = 8</p> <p>Other = 9</p>	
	<p>DEPICTION OF NIGERIAN POLICE</p>	

No Mention = 0

Brutality on citizens
= 1

Cause of the problem
= 2

Assault on protesters
= 3

Assault on media personnel
= 4

Assault on police
= 5

Other= 6

Table 1 indicates the coding categories as well as the major frames used for the coding of text content from the earlier mentioned organisations intended for the study. The ‘protesters frame’ indicates how textual news reports that involved the protesters will be coded for. The ‘government frame’ however, indicates the textual news reports that involved government officials, the government as a body, and the Nigerian Police. The numbers assigned to each item under each major category are the codes that will allow for further comprehension of media portrayal.

Table 2: Coding Sheet/Schedule

NAME:										
DATE:										
CODING SHEET / SCHEDULE										
HEADLINE:										
WRITER/REPORTER:										
DATE:										
NWP	MO	SRL	PON	TNC	CSE	DOP	RFP	SMP	DOG	DNP

Table 2 shows the coding sheet used for the data collection process. By design, this form is constructed to collect data from open-ended items in the coding manual. The coding manual further identifies the abbreviated letters positioned at the top of the empty cells.

Data Scraping for the Quantification of Tweets

The use of a well-authenticated software programme is pivotal to scraping an intended large sum of Twitter data. As established earlier, the study intends to quantify earlier earlier-mentioned hashtags by way of counting tweets and retweets from Twitter. This will be achieved through [Graphext.com](https://www.graphext.com). Graphext is an advanced analytics tool used to capture data for several professional purposes.

3.4 Limitation of Methods

For this research, I made use of online newspapers and news media textual content from international media sources. This is due to the cost limitations and the distance of Nigeria from the UK. Due to a long waiting period for a Twitter API approval, I made use of a data scraping / mining software PRO account which allowed me access to all necessary data needed for the study.

3.5 Strengths

The accessibility and non-perishable nature of published text on the world wide web remains an advantage to researchers, especially in cases of conducting research remotely. The developer accessibility of Twitter aided vehemently in the research.

3.6 Ethical Concerns

As stated earlier, this study is explicitly quantitative and makes no use of human participants. Using a well-engineered data scraping software like Graphext to locate raw tweets created by individuals is a cause for concern on its own. This further raises a concern about the premise of user privacy (Weinhardt, 2021). However, the Twitter ‘privacy setting’ (Twitter, 2022) informs users of possible use of public data with partners or other API’s. The quantification of tweets and retweets is only what is included in this study to predict engagement within the given time period. This does not present a risk of user identity disclosure, as quantitative studies are “relatively easy to make records anonymous and to report findings in ways that don’t allow individuals to be identified” (Bryman, 2021). This, not including private messages, has settled

the issue of consent. Furthermore, the study employs Rivers and Lewis' (2014) recommendations that data which is at risk of exposing tweet authors should not be included in the research. On that note, the names and other personal information of the tweet authors will not be included in the completed research reports. The Ethics Form is located in Appendix 1.

CHAPTER 4

4.0 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS 4.1 Quantitative Content Analysis of Text Publications

The entirety of the coding process of 181 online text publications from the selected sample units will ultimately aid to understand the pattern of news coverage during the #EndSARS protest. Furthermore, the final results from the analysis will then prove or disprove the pattern of protest paradigm in the method of report and coverage.

After the initial coding and intra-coder reliability testing, the aid of 5 coders were implored and 10 percent of the coded text (6) were selected at random to be tested. Using the instructions of the coding manual, the coders were guided. To test inter-coder reliability involved the use of ‘Percentage Agreement’ formula (as noted in; Rose, Spinks & Ana, 2015). That is:

$$PA = A/n \times 100$$

An 80% agreement on the coded results were achieved. This means that 4 out of 5 coders agreed on the coded results.

4.2 Frequency of Coded Categories

Figure 1: Coding Categories According to Coverage

The nodes on the line graph represent the exact record of data, meanwhile the colours represent the categories shown below the graph. The illustration above shows the total frequency of news reports that involved the #EndSARS protest from 8 October 2020 to 6 November 2020 as established earlier. The

Guardian Newspaper had the highest coverage which was 50. Arise News had 10, Nigerian Tribune had 36, This Day had 11, The Nation had 34, BBC had 38, and CNN had 2.

The max coverage consists of the Story Length, Position of News content, and

Type of News content. They are illustrated as one in figure 1 because the frequencies are all the same. This means that all text publications, no absence was recorded. Furthermore, to aid in understanding Figure 1, the list according to category is provided below with numeric assignments in exact frequency.

- **Cases:**
The Guardian=45, Arise News=9, Nigerian Tribune=28, This Day=11, The Nation=32, BBC=38, CNN=2.
- **Depiction Of Protesters:**
The Guardian=43, Arise News=8, Nigerian Tribune=32, This Day=10, The Nation=30, BBC=37, CNN=2.
- **Reason For Protest:**
The Guardian=29, Arise News=6, Nigerian Tribune=5, This Day=2, The Nation=8, BBC=34, CNN=2.
- **Social Media Usage:**
The Guardian=31, Arise News=4, Nigerian Tribune=5, This Day=5, The Nation=6, BBC=21, CNN=2.
- **Depiction Of Government:**
The Guardian=30, Arise News=7, Nigerian Tribune=21, This Day=3, The Nation=20, BBC=30, CNN=2.
- **Depiction Of Nigerian Police:**
The Guardian=39, Arise News=7, Nigerian Tribune=16, This Day=6, The Nation=12, BBC=31, CNN=2.

4.3 Frequency According to Media Frame Figure

2:

Figure 2 aims to show the most common frequency of codes recorded for depiction of protesters, reason for protest, and social media use. These are the categories that make up the protesters frame. This will help to understand how the protesters were portrayed on the media during the period of coverage used for this study.

To properly understand this illustration, refer to the coding manual. This is because, some categories being coded were closed-ended. That is, yes=1 or no=0. However, other categories were open-ended. Some had up to 14 indications to be coded for.

The Guardian:

36% of ‘depiction of protesters’ indicators coded, implies that The Guardian newspaper mostly portrayed the protesters in a more neutral sense. That is, there were little portrayals of the protesters as violent or perpetuating criminal activities. However, 44% of news reports from The Guardian did not mention the reasons for the protest. Furthermore, 34% of the reports that mentioned the reasons were mostly anchored on ‘Calling for an end to the Special AntiRobbery

Squad'. 60% of reports from The Guardian mentioned the protester's use of social media to amplify the protest.

Arise News:

The study revealed that 40% of Arise News reports in the depiction of protest coding category mainly made mention of the protest's international reach and how the Nigerian diaspora rallied for support in countries of residence. For instance, the UK, America, and Canada. 20% of reports made mention of the activists who were involved, and 20% made mention of protesters in a generic manner. 40% of reports mentioned reasons for protesting, and an equal 40% had no mentions of any reasons. There was a 60% absence of the use of social media in the reports. However, there was a 40% mention of the use of social media during the protest. This tallies with the 40% of international reach which was recorded, which implies the use of social media to achieve global recognition.

Nigeria Tribune:

42% of Nigeria Tribune's reports only made mention of the activists, according to the depiction of protesters category in the coding manual. However, I further discovered that there was an 86% omission on mentioning reasons for the protest. There was equally an 86% omission on the use of social media.

This Day:

73% of reports from This Day during the studied period made mention of the protesters but in a derogatory way. The 73% of these reports majorly emphasised on the spread of criminal activities as a result of the protest, and also implied that the protesters were the cause of major disturbances and destruction of property. However, the reason for protest category recorded 9% mention and 82% omissions. There were 55% omissions in reporting the use of social media, and 45% worth of reports that indicated the use of social media.

The Nation:

50% of reports from the Nation implied the mix up of criminals and criminal activities as a result of the protest in the depiction of protesters category. There was 79% omission in indicating any reasons for the protest, and 18% in indicating human rights issues. However, 82% of reports within that period omitted the mention of social media usage by protesters and activists.

BBC:

45% of text publications from BBC mainly made neutral mention of the protesters, while 42% made mention of activists in the forefront of the protests both on the street and on social media. Meanwhile, 79% of BBC reports mainly suggests the reason for the protest as a human rights issue. Furthermore, 55% of the reports imply the use of social media during the protest by the protesters as a way to communicate and amplify their voices.

CNN:

CNN only had two text-publicised reports within this period. This is because most of the coverage by CNN were eyewitness and foreign correspondence videos. However, all categories were filled, leaving a 100% total. A 100% neutral depiction of protest, 100% report on the reason for protest that implies Human Rights, and 100% mention of social media use during the protest.

Figure 3:

Just like figure 2, figure 3 aims to show the most common frequency coded for the depiction of government category and depiction of Nigeria police category. In this case, these categories make up the Nigerian government framing. The ultimate purpose of this illustration is to aid in understanding how the media portrayed the Nigerian government during the #EndSARS protest.

The Guardian:

40% of news reports from The Guardian omitted mention of the government, 26% made mention of the government against the protest, as in by mention of government officials who rebuked activists and demonstrators. 10% of the reports mentioned government officials that supported the protest. However, under the category of Nigerian police depiction, 28% of reports mentioned the Nigerian police as a cause of the problem, and 24% made mention of a more generic portrayal of the police.

Arise News:

The study revealed 40% of reports from Arise News' coverage during the 30day period depicted the Nigerian government as being responsible for criminal activities during the protest, 30% of reports made no mention of the government at all, and 20% made a generic mention of government officials. Under the category for police depiction, 60% of reports was geared towards the Nigerian police as cause of the problem.

Nigerian Tribune:

58% of reports from the Nigerian Tribune depicted the Nigerian government on a generic note, that is; random indications of government officials as regards to the protest without affiliations to any category indicators. However, the study revealed 42% of government depiction in reports were omitted. For the depiction of the Nigerian police, 56% of reports omitted mention of the Nigerian police, 39% made generic mentions, not affiliated to coding categories.

This Day:

The study revealed 73% of reports from This Day daily newspaper made mention of Government officials against the protest, including the Nigerian President. Discovered, was 27% of the reports which had generic and random mentions of government officials like the Nigerian Minister for Information.

The depiction of Nigerian police had 45% omission of mentions, and equally 45% of random unaffiliated mentions, and only had 10% indication of police brutality on citizens.

The Nation:

59% of The Nation's reports in the depiction of government category had indications of government officials without context. For instance, these reports made mention of government officials engaging in other state's affairs while the protest was ongoing. The study also found 41% of reports omitted Government or Government officials' mentions.

However, the depiction of Nigerian police category had 65% omission of mentions in reports, with 24% random indications.

BBC:

The study found that 76% of reports from the BBC within the analysed period indicates accountability of the Nigerian Government, in that the government should be held accountable for the massacre of unarmed, peaceful protesters. 37% of reports in the context of the Nigerian police's depiction indicated police brutality on Nigerian citizens, and 26% of reports indicated the police as the cause of the problem.

CNN:

The two news text publications gathered from CNN within the specified period showed a 100% indication for accountability of the Nigerian government, and 100% indication of the Nigerian police as cause of the problem. This is perhaps because CNN's reports involved a lot of eyewitness, surveillance, and foreign correspondence. It could also be the reason behind why the Nigerian Government threatened sanction on CNN.

With 95 indications, the analysis ultimately revealed 52% of reports published had a storylength of 300-500 words. Furthermore, 75% of published text were news stories. The frequency of codes from all analysed news reports indicating '1 = responsible for criminal activities during protest, 3 = mix-up of criminals during protest, and 0 = no mention/invalid' in the Depiction of Protesters category, and codes indicating '0 = no mention/invalid' in the Reason for Protest category revealed 77% of omissions and negative portrayal of #EndSARS protesters. These reports are those published by the National print media outlets which consist of private owned and government owned establishments. As seen in the break-down of new reports from the international news media, they provided more transparent reports on the protesters demands and reasons for the protest.

5.0 QUANTIFICATION OF TWITTER HASHTAGS

Table 1: Quantification of Tweets and Retweets

(#) HASHTAGS	TWEETS	RETWEETS
#EndSARS	1,286,741	7,971,334
#endsars	798,374	3,306,233
#endpolicebrutality	1,109,278	4,438,954
#endpolicebrutalityinnigeria	658,845	3,087,646
#endsarsimmediately	312,911	1,498,440
#endsarsnow	768,680	3,417,151
#endsarsprotest	259,305	888,126
#endswat	662,575	3,098,836
#sarsmustgo	433,654	2,400,183
#sarsmustendnow	207,149	732,558
Total:	6,497,512	31,039,452

As earlier established, Graphext is an advanced analytic tool used to capture data for several professional purposes. The software programme is not limited to location. This means, it is capable of scrapping accessible worldwide social media data. Using the data scrapping software Graphext, a total of 37.5 million actions were achieved. As seen on table 1, that is a total of 6,497,512 tweets and 31,039,452 retweets. In order to achieve this, the social media data scrapping tool scrapped public twitter data from the periods counting 8

October 2020 to 6 November 2020. However, while analysing the data, the software identified timelines and frequencies. In this case, it was discovered that the use of these hashtags differed according to timeline and frequency, and each had periods of spikes in user engagement.

Figure 1: Frequency Of #EndSARS Usage

Figure 2: Frequency of #endsars Usage

Figure 1 and 2 shows frequency of the ‘#EndSARS’ and ‘#endsars’ usage during the selected timeframe. It counts from 8 October 2020 to 6 November 2020. This illustration is particularly interesting. First, for the similarities, but most importantly because of the spikes in frequency which signify key events during the protest. On 11 October 2020, the Nigeria Police Chief announced the dissolution of the infamous police unit, but on the same day introduced a new unit named SWAT- Special Weapons and Tactics Team. This fuelled and aggravated the protesters more. However, as established in the Literature review, this was not the first time Nigerians were promised police reforms. On 17 October 2020, Nigerians living in the UK and other supporters came together to demonstrate peacefully in the UK. On 20 October 2020, the Lagos State Government imposed a 24-hour curfew which was disregarded by protesters. The

same protesters who were later shot at, late on the same day. The visible gaps between the three major spikes indicate less than 1000 frequency of usage during this period. However, the pickup after each gap reflects the Habermas' (1964) 'public sphere'.

Figure 3: Frequency of #endpolicebrutality Usage

Figure 4: Frequency of #endpolicebrutalityinnigeria Usage

The use of the hashtags '#endpolicebrutality' and 'endpolicebrutalityinnigeria' were almost used synonymously. However, Figure 3 indicates that '#endpolicebrutality' was used more

frequently before the first major spike of ‘#endpolicebrutalityinnigeria’ occurred on 12 October 2020 as seen in figure 4. This could be relative to the #BlackLivesMatter protests against police brutality which occurred earlier the same year and had Nigerians being relatable and in support. Furthermore, these hashtags share a major similarity from 23 October 2020 where minimal ambiance of frequency was maintained.

Figure 5: Frequency of #endsarsimmediately Twitter Usage

Figure 6: Frequency of #endsarsnow Twitter Usage

Figure 9: Frequency of #sarsmustend

Figure 10: Frequency of #sarsmustendnow Twitter Usage

One significant discovery from analysing the Twitter data is the peak of frequency of hashtag usage and the plummet much later. In figures 1 to 10,

We see the progression of hashtags from 8 October 2020 to 20 October 2020. From 21 October 2020, we notice the significant drop in frequency of hashtag usage. This drop is noticed a day

after the '20-10-20 Lekki Toll Gate Massacre'. Perhaps the drop in frequency is because of the abrupt halt of street demonstrations after the Lekki Toll Gate incidence. However, the low frequency of hashtag usage seen in figures 5 to 10 do not exceed 5000 tweets and retweets. The hashtag usage in figures 1 and 2 both maintain a visible minimal frequency of up to 20,000 tweets and retweets afterwards. Perhaps this explains the reason why the hashtags '#EndSARS' and '#endsars' maintained as the most identifiable hashtags for the #EndSARS movement.

CHAPTER 6

6.0 CONCLUSION

Citizens and marginalised groups turn to protests when they feel they are not being heard, or their demands are not being met. As argued in the review of literature, protests have brought about significant change in systems where the protesting groups feel marginalized. An example is the #MeTooMovement, #BlackLivesMatter, and #EndSARS campaign. However, scholars and researchers alike have long debated on how traditional news media tends to portray political unrests. Chan and Lee's (1984) 'protest paradigm' explains the pattern of further marginalization and downplay of protesters, activists, and their causes, by the news media. Lee (2014) further suggests 'description biases' as methods of political protest coverage where the news media deliberately selects parts of the protest, they feel is newsworthy. In this case, the negative parts. This is exhaustively explained in Smith et.al (2001) study that revealed protests which featured arrest of protesters, violence on protesters, and counterdemonstrations only ever generated episodic coverage, which did not focus on underlining issues such as the reason for the protest or what the protesters are demanding for.

Ultimately, this study revealed a large extent to which national news reports on the #EndSARS protesters were portrayed in line with criminal activities, destruction of property, and public disturbances. From the analysis, less than 30% of the reports identified the 'reason for protest'. The study also echoed Smith et.al (2001) theory on 'episodic coverage' as well. However, the international news media coverage was more transparent in reporting the reasons for the protest, as well as reasons behind the political unrest. This fits perfectly into Muratoglu's (2021) claim on how international news media tend to cover political protests in third-world countries. It also furthers Olasoji's (2020) claim that the media had declared themselves on the side of the Nigerian government. In conclusion, the absence of proper news media coverage on the protest and the negative portrayal of the protesters proved Chan and Lee's (1984) 'protest paradigm' pattern during the 2020 #EndSARS protest.

The research further affirmed Lee's (2014) claim of how activists turn to alternative media in times of political unrest and media bias. In this case, twitter. In the literature review, we garnered the use of 'hashtag activism' for several other protests, and most recently, the 2020

#EndSARS protest of Nigeria. The review also establishes the achievements of these protests despite poor or negative coverage by traditional news media. This is because of the use and amplification of social media to raise awareness for moral, social, and political causes. This claim further implies Habermas' (1992) 'public sphere' where basically, individuals come together regardless of profession and class, and create discourses based on interests.

Twitter has provided a space where individuals are permitted to use 'uncolorful language' to communicate and build discourse, especially on political issues, thus Obia (2020) offers a convincing argument on the concept of 'Twittersphere'. Perhaps this has become the reason for so much academic research on Twitter in recent time. This study analysed and quantified tweets generated using a selected number of hashtags used during the #EndSARS protest. The analysis on these randomly selected hashtags revealed a summed total of 37.5 million tweets generated during the span of 30 days. Note, the figure is only achieved from the random samples, and not the entirety of hashtags used during the period of political unrest. Perhaps these further buttresses other researchers' claims of the #EndSARS protest gaining more global awareness and twitter engagement than the #BlackLivesMatter protest (e.g., Obia, 2020; Hillary, 2020). This does not only prove the 'public sphere' concept, but ultimately answers the research question on the extent Twitter was used to achieve global awareness during the #EndSARS protest.

Furthermore, the study revealed a pattern of protesters' disregard by the government, amidst poor media coverage. This is seen in the cases of the #EndSARS protest of 2020 and the Cuban protest of 2021, where the government stated that the news about the protests circulating online were fake and should be disregarded despite affirmation by international news media sources. Having established this, it is a necessity for further and broadened research on the concepts of protest paradigm, selection bias, Twittersphere, and the relationship between traditional news media and protesters in times of political unrest.

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